

Unique Positive Solution of Nonlinear Fractional Differential Equation Boundary Value Problem

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Abstract : By using two new fixed point theorems for mixed monotone operators, the positive solution of nonlinear fractional differential equation boundary value problem is studied. Its existence and uniqueness is proved, and an iterative scheme is constructed to approximate it.

Keywords : fractional differential equation, boundary value problem, positive solution, existence and uniqueness, fixed point theorem, mixed monotone operator

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